

Factors influencing Farmers Access to Agricultural Extension Service: evidence from coffee large scale demonstration clusters in Sidama region, Ethiopia

*Wasihun Alemnew

Department of Agricultural Extension, Wondogenet Agricultural Research Center, Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, Wondogenet, Ethiopia.

*Corresponding author: **WASIHUN ALEMNEW**

Department of Agricultural Extension, Wondogenet Agricultural Research Center, Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research, Wondogenet, Ethiopia.

Abstract

This research paper attempts to determine access to agricultural extension service on the coffee large scale demonstration by Food System Resilience Program (FSRP) in Shebedino and Aleta chuko districts. Research on factors affecting access to extension service on coffee large scale demonstrations within the farmers is influenced by different factors perspective and integrated research for development. This study applied a cross-sectional research design; the data was collected within one year. A sampling frame was constructed by enlisting all the farmers who were demonstrating coffee in the study area. A multivariate probit model was employed to evaluate the determinants of the access to extension service to farmers. The model includes nine explanatory variables: age, sex, household size, education, access to agricultural information, farming experience, farm size, road access, and total income. Furthermore, Table 2 reveals that among the nine explanatory variables tested, four variables: - Gender, educational status, farming experience, Road access and agricultural information were statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$ and 0.01 , respectively. The agricultural extension service in Ethiopia is crucial for delivering expert scientific support to farmers.

Keywords: Extension service, Factors influencing, Coffee, Large scale demonstration, Farmers.

1. Introduction

In various regions worldwide, agricultural production growth generally hovers around 1.0% annually over extended periods (Udemezue and Osegbue, 2018). In Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), agriculture serves as the primary source of livelihood for most of the population (Yohannes Girma and Berhanu Kuma, 2021). While agriculture in Ethiopia offers significant employment and promotes rural development alongside food production, its advancement and growth remain critical development priorities (Reza Anik *et al.*, 2020). Additionally, the agricultural landscape in Ethiopia is marked by a high number of smallholder farmers compared to a limited number of commercial producers (Belay Kasa and Dawit Alemu, 2016). Cereals dominate as the principal food crop, both in terms of land area and production volume, representing 95% of the country's agricultural output and contributing 86.68% to grain production (Dawit Milkias, 2020). Extension is derived from Latin word and refers to educating farmers living in rural areas through education offered in FTC, Farmer schools, colleges, and universities. To put it another way, Extension uses the fundamental ideas of "learning by doing" and "seeing believes" to assist individuals in assisting themselves (According to Sahoo *et al.*, 2021). Agricultural information also is defined as the data for decision making and a resource that must be acquired and used to make an informed decision and can be sourced from different actors; including public sectors such as research, extension, and universities, cooperatives, and individual farmers (Tewodros Ayalew and Tesfaye Abebe, 2018).

Agricultural extension service in Ethiopia formally begun half a century ago in the 1950's with the establishment of the Imperial Ethiopian College of Agriculture and Mechanical Arts (ECAMA) now called Haramaya University, Informal beginning of extension service dating back to 1931 with the establishment of the Ambo agricultural school, which is one of the oldest institutions offering general education with major emphasis on agriculture (Tefaye Gemechu, 2017).

Similar Rashid et al., (2021), reported that separated to agricultural extension services have been shown to build farmers agricultural knowledge and skills, disseminate new technology and change farmers attitudes. As regard to the effects and the emergence of agricultural growth is critical for industrialization and economic growth in the 1960s, however, the process of agricultural growth itself has remained outside the concern of the most developing economics (Udemezue and Osegbue, 2018).

Extension policy in Ethiopia has been exclusively production - focused, institutionally monolithic, centrally directed, and organized only model farmers have been consulted by extension agents while the marginalized and poor remain ignored (Mengal et al., 2017). According to Muluken Gezahegn (2019), The Comprehensive Package Programs (CPPs) in the period 1967–1971; the Minimum Package Projects (MPPs) in the period 1971–1985; the Peasant Agricultural Development Program (PADEP) in the period 1985–1995; and, the Participatory Demonstration and Training Extension System (PADETES) – later renamed as national agricultural extension intervention program – in the period 1995 to date. The implemented programs provided relevant agricultural information and appropriate technologies, notably improved crop varieties that could improve productivity and household income (Elias *et al.*, 2016). In the same way, the study confined by Udemezue and Osegbue (2018), the integrated approach to improving the environment and well-being of the people of the community. An earlier view of extension emphasized scientific research as the main driver of innovation, creating new knowledge and technology that can be transferred and adapted to various situations (Asfaw Albor, 2018).

Research on innovation and development processes within the agricultural sector is influenced by different factors perspective and integrated research for development (Onumah *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, the transfer of information on science and technology in the agricultural field plays a vital role in order for farmers to utilize current knowledge and to enhance their economy through the linkage of different stakeholders (Teka Debele *et al.*, 2019). Interrelated to this, according to Atrsaw Anteneh *et al.*, (2022), the improved production technology package includes land preparation, crop rotation, improved seed, sowing method, seed rate, timing of fertilizer application, rate of fertilizer application, weeding frequency, disease prevention, pest prevention, harvesting time, threshing method, and storage system. Although, knowledge-intensive technologies require effective extension service to achieve the desired outputs on the agriculture sector (Singh *et al.*, 2019). As the extension worker is the main source of information and training of farmers in adopting new extension packages, their frequent contact with farmers is important for achieving the effectiveness of the extension services (Elias *et al.*, 2016).

In general, access to extension service needs different stakeholders to enhancing the impact of new technologies for farmers. Hence, to facilitate technology development and delivery from research centers through extension organizations to farmers, there is a need for strong links between research, extension and farmers. Therefore, this study aimed to analyse factors that affect access to extension service in agricultural technology transfer.

2. Methodology

This study applied a cross-sectional research design; the data was collected within one year (one-time research). A survey research design was used in this study. Moreover, a cross-sectional survey was employed, in which data was collected at a specific point in time. Shebedino and Aleta Chucko is one of the important districts where old coffee rejuvenated with improved varieties demonstrated on a large scale. A sampling frame was constructed by enlisting all the farmers who were demonstrating coffee in the study area.

The study area was selected purposefully from Sidama Region for this study. Firstly, coffee is the most important cash crop in the districts. Wondogenet Agricultural Research Center (WGARC) is one of the most frequently technology demonstrated sites, where extension programs have been implemented for a relatively longer period of time in the research center. Although all core extension activities and the presence of functional agencies involved in agricultural technology transfer were run either by research institutes or agricultural extension in a extension service context. Farmers were chosen for this study using a simple random sample technique that had been used one of the access to extension service on the chosen commodity. The size of the sample depends on precision, and there is no single rule that can be used to determine sample size, but a larger sample is much more likely to be representative of the population.

The required sample size of household respondents would be calculated using the formula Yamane (1967:886) below, due to its simplicity and predetermination population.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)} = \frac{300}{1+300(0.05^2)}, \quad n=172$$

N= the population size (300), n=Sample size, e= level of precision 5% for confidence level of 95%. The sampling frame was prepared from the selected kebeles of Dobe toga, Holoso and Kore have a total of 300 farm households from those households 172 households was surveyed proportionally using Yamane formula.

Questionnaires, focus group discussions and key informants were used as data collection tools. Interview schedule methods were used to collect primary data like socio-demographic characteristics of respondents, and factors that

influence farmers' access to extension service in coffee production who were willing to provide valuable information. The qualitative data was also collected by face-to-face interviews with the selected key informant respondents, who were voluntarily willing to provide valuable information. The multivariate probit model (MVP) was popular classic model for studying interactions of multiple entities. A multivariate probit model was employed to evaluate the determinants of the access to extension service to farmers. Multinomial models are appropriate when they choose more than one outcome from among a set of mutually exclusive, collectively exhaustive alternatives (Ermias, 2021). According to Gebre *et al.*, (2015), MNL regression is employed to estimate the effect of explanatory variables on factors affecting extension service for technology transfer. The model is normally estimated using the iterative maximum likelihood estimation procedure, which yields unbiased, efficient, and consistent parameter estimates. The equation of the multinomial logistic/probit regression model requires the independent irrelevant alternative assumption (IIA). It indicates that the probability of using certain participation options by a given household needs to be independent of the probability of choosing another extension service option.

Table 1 : Summary of variables, description, expected sign, and their measurements

Variables	Description	Measurement units	Expected sign		
Dependent variables					
Extension service	Perceive access to agricultural extension services	1 for the accessed, 0 otherwise			
Independent variables					
Sex	Sex of the household head	1 if male, 0 otherwise	(-)	(-)	(+/-)
Age	Age of the household head	Number of years	(-)	(+/-)	(+/-)
Household Size	Number of family in the household	Number	(+)	(+)	(+)
Educational status	The educational status of the household	Year of schooling	(+)	(+)	(+)
farm experience	Farmers engaged in coffee farm	Number of years	(-)	(+)	(+)
Distance to main road	Distance from residence to road	Minute	(-)	(-)	(-)
Information	Coffee technology information	1= Yes ,0 = No	(+)	(+)	(+)
Farm siz	Coffee land holdings	1=Yes, 0 = no	(+)	(+)	(+)
Total income	Total household income	ETB	(-)	(+)	(+/-)
Total land size	Total land size of the household	Hectare	(+)	(+/-)	(+)

3. Result and discussions

Table-2 presents the results of a regression analysis examining the socio-economic factors that affect farmers' access to agricultural extension services during the implementation of coffee demonstration projects using a cluster farming approach. The model includes nine explanatory variables: age, sex, household size, education, access to agricultural information, farming experience, farm size, road access, and total income. Furthermore, Table 2 reveals that among the nine explanatory variables tested, four variables: - Gender, educational status, farming experience, Road access and agricultural information were statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$ and 0.01 , respectively.

The study reported a Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) ranging from 1.0 to 1.8, which, according to Akinwande *et al.* (2015), suggests that the independent variables are not correlated. Multicollinearity can inflate the standard errors of the coefficients excessively, leading to some variables appearing statistically insignificant when they should not (Murray *et al.*, 2012). The -2 log likelihood built from 95.66 with only the constant to -2.135, with a chi-square value of 215 and 11 degrees of freedom, showing statistical significance at $p \leq 0.034$. The Cox and Snell R^2 and Nagelkerke R^2 values were 0.57 and 0.68, respectively, indicating that the model's predictors explained approximately 57% to 68% of the variance in respondents' access to extension services during the large-scale demonstrations (Table 2). Additionally, the Hosmer-Lemeshow test yielded a chi-square value of 12.204 with 8 degrees of freedom and a p-value of 0.142. According to Pallant (2011), a p-value greater than 0.005 indicates a good fit between the model and the data, which holds true for this analysis.

Table-2 : factors influencing farmers' access to effective extension service during the implementation of coffee demonstration in Sidama region

Variable	B	S. E	wald	Sig.	Exp(B)	Predicted change %	VIF
Age	-0.324	0.561	0.483	0.44	1.376	34.6	1.836
Sex	0.319	0.417	0.588	0.05	0.677	-42.3	1.120
Household size	0.148	0.847	0.430	0.64	1.146	16.4	1.380?
Education	0.144	0.384	0.183	0.01	1.778	12.100	1.213
Farming experience	0.133	0.763	0.172	0.04	1.433	27.8	1.476
Farm size	0.018	0.875	0.001	0.78	1.117	5.4	1.732
Distance to main road	0.12	0.605	0.04	0.09	1.127	12.75	1.078
Total annual income	0.031	0.071	0.088	0.06	1.04	168.2	1.162
Information	0.23	0.504	0.002	0.01	1.14	5	1.171
Constant	-2.135	1.483	1.706	0.23	0.106	-75.2	

Dependent variable: Perceive access to agricultural extension services (1=Access, 0=Do not access)

Gender: The gender of the respondents had a beta coefficient of 0.319 and was statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$. This suggests that female respondents were less likely than male respondents to perceive the effectiveness of extension services during the implementation of large-scale coffee demonstrations, indicating a negative predicted change of 42%. Solomon Yokamo (2020) supports this finding, particularly in developing countries, where male-headed households typically have better opportunities to participate in training and workshops, gaining greater exposure to information that facilitates the adoption of improved technology compared to female-headed households. The author also notes that due to various sociocultural values and norms, males often experience greater freedom in mobility and participation in extension programs, leading to better access to information. The study's findings are influenced by several factors, including the nature and composition of agricultural extension agents. Observations in the surveyed regions indicated a male-dominated extension system with biased attitudes, which limited female access to agricultural extension services. This aligns with Ragasa *et al.* (2012) in Ethiopia, who found that female farmers were less likely to receive extension services compared to their male counterparts.

Age: The age of respondents had a negative beta coefficient of -0.324 but was not statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$. This indicates that as respondents aged by one year, their likelihood of perceiving the effectiveness of extension services during the implementation of large-scale coffee demonstrations decreased by 35%. This finding is consistent with a study by Abdalah and Awal (2016) in Ghana, which noted that age had limited effects on access to agricultural extension services and technology adoption. According to Demeke and Haji (2014), older farmers often lack access to market information, whereas younger farmers tend to have better access to price information and can sell a larger portion of their products.

Farmers' Educational Status: The educational level of the respondents showed a beta coefficient of 0.144, indicating that an increase of one unit in respondents' educational status resulted in a 120% positive change in their likelihood of perceiving the effectiveness of extension services during the implementation of coffee large-scale demonstrations. Furthermore, this variable was statistically significant at $p \leq 0.01$. Education is recognized as a critical factor influencing the decision to adopt new agricultural technologies (Tewodros Ayalew and Tesfaye Abebe, 2018). Education enhances farmers' abilities to obtain and analyze information, enabling more informed marketing decisions (Abebaw Abebe, 2017). Ayalew and Abebe (2018) also revealed that farmers' education levels significantly impact the efficiency of information flow and technology adoption rates. Consequently, awareness helps determine farmers' capacity for information seeking and the use of improved technologies. Elias *et al.* (2016) argue that better educational status allows farmers to utilize extension services more effectively, while Reza Anik *et al.* (2020) emphasize that education is vital for enhancing the capacity to absorb both existing and new technologies.

Farming Experience: The findings indicate that farming experience correlates with respondents' likelihood of perceiving the effectiveness of extension services after the coffee demonstration was implemented. This variable had a positive beta coefficient of 0.133, suggesting that each unit increase in farming experience corresponds to an 28% positive change in the likelihood of accessing effective extension services during coffee large-scale demonstrations. It

was statistically significant at $p \leq 0.04$. These findings inline with Chauke *et al.* (2013) in South Africa, who found that access to credit diminished with an increase in certain variables, such as farming experience, repayment periods, risk, uncertainty, distance to lenders, and asset accumulation. Evidence shows that extension services that accommodate the diverse interests, needs, and capacities of farmers can lead to increased agricultural production and improved food security (Geriba Leta *et al.*, 2020). The extension system tends to prioritize farmers who are older and more experienced (Muluken Gezahegn, 2019).

Annual Income: Farmers' income levels are pivotal for determining their purchasing ability for agricultural inputs, particularly for more advanced technologies that tend to be costly (Tewodros Ayalew and Tesfaye Abebe, 2018). The analysis revealed a positive beta coefficient of .031 for respondents' total annual income, indicating that an increase in this income correlates with a 168% increase in the likelihood of perceiving the effectiveness of extension services during coffee demonstration implementation. However, this result was not statistically significant at $p \leq 0.06$. This outcome aligns with findings from Noel *et al.* (2018) in Tanzania, which noted that the annual household income of smallholder farmers significantly affects their access to extension services. Similarly, Negese Tamirat and Jemal Abafita (2021) established that adopting technologies—such as improved varieties and row planting—led to increased income for crop-farming households in Ethiopia.

Land Holdings: Additionally, respondents' farm sizes showed a positive beta coefficient, indicating that a unit increase in farm size resulted in a predicted 5% increase in the likelihood of perceiving the effectiveness of extension services during large-scale coffee demonstrations ($B=0.018$, predicted change=5.4). This finding contrasts with Dazdze *et al.* (2012) in Abura-Asebu Kwamankese, Ghana, where farm size significantly impacted farmers' access to agricultural credit. A larger land area increases participation in extension activities (Wasihun Alemnew, 2022). Solomon Yokamo (2020) also noted that farmers with larger farms are more likely to adopt improved agricultural technologies compared to their smaller-land counterparts. Households with more extensive land holdings are often better off due to the ability to produce surplus goods for sale beyond subsistence needs (Demeke and Haji, 2014). Additionally, those with larger land sizes are more likely to adopt new agricultural technologies (Mamaru Tesfaye and Paulos Gutema, 2022).

Household Size: The household size of respondents yielded a positive beta coefficient of 0.148, suggesting that an increase in household size correlates with a 16% increase in the likelihood of perceiving the effectiveness of extension services during the implementation of coffee large-scale demonstrations. Generally, respondents with larger households viewed the effectiveness of these services more favorably than those with smaller households; however, this variable was not statistically significant at $p \leq 0.046$. This result contradicts findings from Abdalah and Awal (2016) in Ghana, which indicated that household size significantly influenced access to agricultural extension services. Larger families are more likely to implement extension advice, such as varying cultivation systems, thus boosting agricultural productivity (Elias *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, family size is found to correlate positively with participation in mechanisms that support labor for technology demonstrations (Wasihun Alemnew, 2022). Larger households can alleviate labor constraints during the introduction of new technologies (Solomon Yokamo, 2020).

Road Access: Mideksa Fufa and Desalegh Yadeta (2020) highlight the critical role of roads in market development, facilitating input distribution and posing significant infrastructural challenges to agricultural advancement. Proximity to main roads enhances farmers' access to research findings, although it can lead to a bias in research and extension services (Alivi and Mengistu, 2008). Solomon Yokamo (2020) also noted that road access connects rural farmers to markets, enhancing their ability to transport produce. However, Ethiopia's fragmented land tenure and the distances between home and fields complicate the transport of organic fertilizers (Geriba Leta *et al.*, 2020).

Access to Agricultural Information: Solomon Yokamo (2020) posits that access to information is crucial in fostering the adoption of improved agricultural technologies. Effective information-sharing among farmers, extension workers, and researchers is key to facilitating new technology adoption (Tewodros Ayalew and Tesfaye Abebe, 2018). Providing comprehensive information to farmers plays an essential role in their successful adoption of new agricultural practices (Kaur, M., and Kaur, R., 2019). Efficient communication between agricultural research and extension services—marked by regular interactions and shared objectives—enhances service delivery for users (Urhibo, 2021). Improving the link between research and extension can enhance extension services through increased farmer engagement in meetings and demonstration farms (Bereir and Mirghani, 2022). The extension agent serves as a liaison between researchers and technology users, thus minimizing the costs associated with disseminating new agricultural information to diverse farmer populations (Solomon Yokamo, 2020). Moreover, direct contacts among development agents, researchers, and farmers have significantly boosted farmers' exposure to modern farming methods (Adesoji and Tunde, 2012).

4. Summary

Many of Ethiopia's government-driven policies aimed at enhancing cereal production and supporting smallholder commercialization have become outdated. A reevaluation of these strategies is essential, focusing on redefining the roles

of both the public and private sectors within the country's agricultural input, extension, and education frameworks. This reevaluation calls for a deep understanding of the complex issues at play, data-driven analysis and policy suggestions, as well as ongoing discussions regarding the advantages and disadvantages of various alternatives and approaches. The agricultural extension service in Ethiopia is crucial for delivering expert scientific support to farmers. The historical development of these services, both globally and within the country, has evolved significantly over time. The prevalence of numerous small-scale family farms highlights the necessity for these extension services. The spread of different extension models is a common feature of agricultural extension work worldwide. Shared interests shape the relationships and economic ties among the government, producers, processors, and extension services. Various types of extension services have been identified based on their purpose, primary objectives, range of activities, training of farmers, methods of operation, human resources, organizational structures, and financing within the agricultural sector.

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5. Reference

1. Abebaw, A. (2017). Factors Affecting use of Information and Communication Technologies for cereal marketing in dembecha woreda, west gojjam zone, Amhara region, Ethiopia (doctoral dissertation, Haramaya University).
2. Adesoji, S. A., & Tunde, A. (2012). Evaluation of the linkage system of research-extension-farmers in Oyo State, Nigeria: Lesson for agricultural extension administrators. *Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development*, 4(20), 561-568.
3. Alivi, S. A. A., & Mengistu, F. (2008). Evaluation of 1st and 2nd generation locally produced seeds of cool season vegetables for vegetable and seed yield at Ankober, Amhara region. In conference on completed crops research activities (Vol. 1, p. 21).
4. Atrsaw Anteneh, A. A., Misganaw, G. S., & Siyum Muluneh, N. (2022). Adoption status and perception of farmers on improved teff technology packages: evidence from east gojjam zone, Ethiopia.
5. Abdallah A and Abdul-rahman A (2016). Determinants of Access to Agricultural Extension Services :Evidence from Smallholder Rural Women in Northern Ghana. *Asian. J. Agric. Exte. Econ. Socio* 9(3):1-8. doi:10.9734/AJAEES/2016/23478.
6. Akinwande MO, Dikko HG, and Samson A (2015). Variance Inflation Factor: As a Condition for the Inclusion of Suppressor Variable (s) in Regression Analysis. *Open J. Stat.*5:754-767.
7. Belay Kasa & Dawit Alemu (2016). Agricultural research and extension linkages: Challenges and intervention options. *Ethiopian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 27(1), 55-76.
8. Bereir & Mirghani. A. (2022). Evaluation of agricultural research, extension and farmers linkages: A case study from Gezira State Sudan. *International Journal of Agricultural Science, Research and Technology in Extension and Education Systems (IJASRT in EESs)*, 12(2), 111-117.
9. Dawit, M. (2020). Factors affecting high yielding teff varieties adoption intensity by small holder farmers in west showa zone, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Economy, Energy and Environment*, 5(1), 6-13.
10. Demeke, L., & Haji, J. (2014). Econometric analysis of factors affecting market participation of smallholder farming in Central Ethiopia.
11. Elias, A., Nohmi, M., Yasunobu, K., & Ishida, A. (2016). Farmers satisfaction with agricultural extension service and its influencing factors: a case study in North West Ethiopia. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Technology*, 18(1), 39-53.
12. Ermias, D. (2021). Econometric analysis of factors affecting market outlet choice of mango fruit producers in Hadero Tunto Zuriya District, Southern Ethiopia. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 7(1), 1891660.
13. Gebre, H., Kindie, T., Girma, M., & Belay, K. (2015). Farmers climate change adaptation options
14. Geriba Leta, Schulz, S., & Alemu, G. G. (2020). Agricultural extension approach: evidence from an Integrated Soil Fertility Management Project in Ethiopia. *Frontiers of Agricultural Science and Engineering*, 7(4), 427-439.
15. Kaur, M., and Kaur, R. (2019). Sources of information of farmers on modern agricultural technology in Punjab: Their status and effectiveness. *Journal of Agricultural Development and Policy*, 29(1), 96-104.
16. Mamaru Tesfaye & Paulos Gutema (2022). Impact of improved forage technology adoption on dairy productivity and household income: a propensity score matching estimation in Northern Ethiopia.
17. Mideksa Fufa & Desalegh Yadeta (2020). Trends and challenges in improved agricultural inputs use by smallholder farmers in Ethiopia: A review. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture-Food Science and Technology*, 8(11), 2286-2292.
18. Muluken Gezahegn (2019). Are farmers in Ethiopia ready to embrace cost-sharing agricultural extension approach?. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 46(9), 1119-1136.
19. Negese Tamirat & Jemal Abafita (2021). Adoption of row planting technology and household welfare in southern Ethiopia, in case of wheat grower farmers in Duna district, Ethiopia. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*, 26(2), 1-12.
20. Noel C.Komba, Malongo R.S. Mlozi , Zebedayo S.K.Mvena, 2018: Socio-economic factors influencing farmers' perception on effectiveness of decentralized agricultural extension information and services delivery in Arumeru District, Tanzania

21. Onumah, J. A., Asante, F. A., & Osei, R. D. (2023). Actor roles and linkages in the agricultural innovation system: options for establishing a cocoa innovation platform in Ghana. *Innovation and Development*, 13(2), 301-322.
22. Reza Anik, A., Rahman, S., & Sarker, J. R. (2020). Five decades of productivity and efficiency changes in world agriculture (1969–2013). *Agriculture*, 10(6), 200.
23. Sahoo, A. K., Sahu, S., Meher, S. K., Begum, R., Panda, T. C., & Barik, N. C. (2021). The role of krishi vigyan Kendras (kvk) in strengthening national agricultural research extension system in India. *Insights into Economics and Management*, 8(9), 43-45.
24. Sinha, S. K., Chander, M., Verma, M. R., & Jena, A. (2019). Factors Affecting Research and Extension Linkage in Veterinary Universities in India. *Indian Journal of Veterinary Sciences and Biotechnology*, 14(4), 63-66.
25. Teka Debele, Gebeyehu, M., & Abebe, A. (2019). Contributions and challenges in research and extension linkage for agricultural transformation in Ethiopia: a review. *International Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 7(2), 187-195.
26. Tewodros Ayalew & Tesfaye Abebe (2018). Agricultural knowledge and technology transfer systems in the Southern Ethiopia. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 13(14), 682-690
27. Udemezue & Osegbue. (2018). Theories and models of agricultural development. *Annals of Reviews and Research*, 1(5), 555574.
28. Yohannes Girma & Berhanu Kuma, (2021) A meta-analysis on the effect of agricultural extension on farmers market participation in Ethiopia. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, 7, 100253.
29. Chauke PK (2013). Factors influencing access to credit: A case study of smallholder farmers in the Capricorn district of South Africa. *A. J. Agric. Res* 8(7): 582–585. doi: 10.5897/AJAR2013.6700
30. Dzadze P, Osei Mensah J, Aidoo R, and Nurah GK (2012). Factors determining access to formal credit in Ghana: A case study of smallholder farmers in the Abura- Asebu Kwamankese district of central region of Ghana. 4(14): 416–423. doi: 10.5897/JDAE12.099.
31. Monela AG (2014). Access to and Adoption of Improved Seeds By Smallholder Farmers in Tanzania. Dissertation for Award of MA in Rural Development at Sokoine University of Agriculture, Morogoro, Tanzania. 88pp.
32. Murray C J L (2012). Supplementary appendix Comprehensive Systematic Analysis of Global Epidemiology: Definitions, Methods, Simplification of DALYs, and Comparative Results from the Global Burden of Disease study 2010', *Lanc* 9859: 1–131. Available at: <https://www.freelists.org/archives/interphen/04-2014/pdfNcqXgOaefH.pdf>.
33. Ragasa C (2012). Gender and Institutional Dimensions of Agricultural Technology Adoption: A Review of Literature and Synthesis of 35 Case Studies. *Int. Assoc. Agric. Econ.* pp. 1–57.
34. Solomon Yokamo (2020). Adoption of improved agricultural technologies in developing countries: literature review. *Int. J. Food Sci. Agric*, 4(2), 183-190.
35. Urhibo, F. A. (2021). Global role dimension of research-extension-farmers linkages in agricultural extension service delivery in selected countries. *Mosogar Journal of Vocational and Technical Education*, 1(1), 114-123.
36. Wasihun Alemnew (2022). Determinants of research-extension-farmers linkage in the process of technology transfer: The Case of Dangila district, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Science*, 7(2), 13-18.